

MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING VOCABULARY

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Abstract: *The article deals with the issues related to analyzing the peculiarities teaching vocabulary and learning strategies based on its integrated usage and also describes modern techniques which can be effective in a foreign language lessons. Enriching the vocabulary of students is the most important task for a foreign language teacher.*

Keywords: *Foreign language, vocabulary, students, lexical skills, communication, communicative language teaching, syntagma.*

A distinctive feature of the modern world is the formation of a community of highly qualified specialists with competitive advantages. Among these advantages can be distinguished professionalism by the experience and knowledge of two or more foreign languages. Optimization of teaching foreign languages can be achieved by studying the language and subject of the specialty on the basis of an integrated course. The role of vocabulary in language learning is difficult to assess. Without knowledge of professional vocabulary, a specialist will not be able to fully communicate and fulfill his professional duties. Currently, due to the wide distribution of the Internet and multimedia technologies, the emphasis in the methodology of teaching foreign languages has shifted from the teacher to the students themselves. Learning is increasingly becoming an interconnected, interdependent process. A qualified specialist begins to realize the need for constant updating and improvement of their language knowledge and competencies. In the methodology of teaching foreign languages, there are a certain number of strategies that facilitate the acquisition of a language. In this article, the author examines in detail strategies that allow replenishing professional vocabulary. The integrated use of vocabulary learning strategies will make it possible to increase professional vocabulary throughout life. In the context of the new socio-economic realities of society, the requirements for the authenticity of foreign language as an instrument of communication in the dialogue of cultures have increased (Milrud 1997). No speech is possible if a person does not store in his memory a sufficient number of words and skills to combine them to achieve a communicative

intention. The student's vocabulary should be in a state of "mobilization readiness" for inclusion in speech (Bim 1998).

Adapted method of the Leitner system – we need to take a stack of flash cards. If the word on the top card is known, then the card is transferred to the end of the pile. If the word is unknown, then after viewing the translation it is transferred to the middle of the pile (closer to the beginning) so that it occurs earlier and more often than words already known. Thus, we achieve a more frequent repetition of the necessary difficult vocabulary and its lasting memorization. We can make flash cards with phrasal verbs and idioms. The site <http://www.english-4kids.com/flashcards.html> has a huge selection of ready-made colorful flash cards. Memory cards The Mind Map memory card is an alternative to traditional methods of processing and transmitting information (notes, short notes, diagrams, etc.) This alternative is more productive, as it has a natural psychological basis, and most importantly turns the student into an active creator of his own knowledge. The psychological basis of the memory card method is associative thinking. The memory card itself, from the point of view of its creators, is a model of the work of our brain. It is enough to reproduce in memory one object of this information card, and it will pull a chain of dozens of interrelated facts, events. So there is a multidimensional associative thinking, which allows you to see not just the object of the world around itself, but in conjunction with other objects. The principles of the memory card There are certain rules for creating memory cards developed by Tony Buchan, which are described in detail in his book "How to Mind Map", namely:

1. The main idea, problem or word is located in the center. Highlighting the keyword of the associative chain, Busan gives almost the main meaning
2. To depict a central idea, you can use drawings, pictures.
3. Each main branch has its own color.
4. Only colored pencils, markers, etc. are used to create maps.
5. The main branches are connected with the central idea, and the branches of the second, third, etc. orders are connected to the main branches.
6. The branches should be curved, not straight (like branches of a tree).
7. Above each line - a branch is written only one keyword. The result of the work is an individual product of one person or one group. Expresses individual capabilities, creates a space for the manifestation of creative abilities.

Benefits of Mental Cards • convenient to use • show the connections between phenomena, the logic of thinking • contribute to better storage of information • collect a large amount of data together • develop creativity, thinking This technique is good to use in group work at the stage of consolidating the lexical material covered on a specific topic.

Rhymes, poems, songs The study of lexical units takes place in a playful way, which contributes to the comfortable state of students in the lesson. Children usually have erratic attention. Therefore, it is imperative in terms of the lesson to provide for types of work that relieve stress, switch the attention of children, cause a positive emotional mood. Learning rhymes, poems meets the age and psychological characteristics of children. They are easy to memorize, possess such characteristics as rhythm, sound repeatability. Learning poetry gives children pleasure. And what is experienced emotionally positively remains in the memory for a long time, leaving a mark on the child's mind. Thanks to rhyme, lexico-grammatical structures are easily activated in oral speech. The crucial point here is the use of an authentic speech pattern, and here songs and poems have many advantages over prose material. They are easy to enter, easy to remember, you can sing in chorus, which removes the psychological press from insecure students. In genuine song material, whole phrases and individual lexical units are often found that are characteristic of colloquial speech. Crosswords Crosswords are a great way for students to activate vocabulary. This strategy can be used in the first lesson of a new topic. Students will remember the words they will use in the next lesson. A crossword puzzle is a great way to repeat the previously learned before the test work. Invite students to create a crossword puzzle based on the new words of the topic they have learned. They will repeat their spelling, remember the meanings. For weak students, you can add a thematic list of words to the crossword puzzle so that they can choose the right ones. Of course, the list of strategies for expanding the vocabulary of students can be continued further, and each teacher will choose those methods that are closer to him. The main thing to remember, work on vocabulary should be constant and systematic.

Using the above vocabulary learning strategies will enable students to replenish their professional vocabulary independently and at any time. It should be noted that these strategies need to be used in a comprehensive manner, since they are interconnected and integrated into each other. Learning professional foreign language vocabulary is a laborious and continuous process. Teachers can help with this by teaching them how to use strategies, but students themselves play an important role. Students should be aware of the vital necessity of learning, constantly use its results in real life and be responsible for it. Only in this interaction can the desired results be achieved.

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